

→ MESS0041: Triple MIMS [P⁸ resolution]

MESS 0047

MIMS 2.54 - Reality Mining - the jewels found when utilizing the realion and source-method mechanism in a philosophæthereal analysis

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ABSTRACT

In two previous works, heavy philosophical lifting was performed, and the combination of the quaternion [Distintian] imaginary number matrix with the PEMF identity led to an intriguing possibility. By use of linear algebraic rules a 2x3 was crossed with the 3x2 from the MIMS 2.10.5 work, which had tentatively identified the W⁵+H matrix with the “six divisions” of Chinese STEMM; and with the 6 powers of the Big G¹. Note, also that this matrix has a large P power component. The combination of the former P⁸ resolution with the Physics (Natural Philosophæ) and Principles makes it a perfect P¹⁰ resolution. Deep mining performed in this work will find other jewels, just as previous mining revealed the G+P+T code²! Also, within the quaternion we see the 1/-1 dichotomy, for which J. Kines has found other “matrix” code evidences³.

Keywords: Philosophy - Source-method Mechanism - MIMS - MIMSilation - realion - GPT code

¹ Explication of the Big G
² MESS0041: Triple MIMS
³ MESSr0002 - Welcome Neo

MIMS 2.54→2.55 The realion 'particle' dissection

"There are more things in Heaven and Earth than dreamt of in your philosophies." ~Shakespeare⁴

A realion is **not a real particle**. It is a virtual, philosophical particle; it only existed in the two previous papers. Today we revive it, not to smash it, vulgarly, but to dissect it. We suspect: inside is the evidence - such as it is - for the Triple Plane Theory⁵, and perhaps, according to Figure 1, the promise of Change Theory⁶. However, the "else" has to be explored elsewhere, pun unintended.

Whereas we 'smashed' the particle last time via algebraic crossing (to be repeated below), in this work we wish to apply a scalpel. Unfortunately, the immediate vulnerability to this desire is to be accused of an [obvious] potential fraud. As we are not Lying Liars Lying Still (or POS Simps⁷), we shall show the obvious:

- ❖ We propose a virtual particle that doesn't exist in reality.
- ❖ We call it a realion.
- ❖ We place it inside a virtual philosophy "no one" has heard of.
- ❖ We 'smash' it, and obtain unique, bizarre codes.
- ❖ We dissect the innards.
- ❖ We 'confirm' our "pre-EPEMC"⁸ hypothesis about the Triple Plane Theory.
 - Even set up the Change Theory we have a 'known bias' for
 - Now we are a) accused of "confirmation bias"
- ❖ We find within the innards what we *appear to the outside world to want to find*
 - Now we are accused of a priori fallacy
- ❖ The spicy commentator determines we are involved in violations of our own EPEMC standards⁹.
- ❖ The even spicier critic claims this shows that the MIMS philosophy is not internally self-consistent.
- ❖ The purely unscientific critic who always goes too far, even acts as a POS Simpreme, uses this to claim the entire MIMS work¹⁰ (not only those touching this work), and even the EPEMC itself is philosophically specious, pseudo-scientific or *ascientific* 'drivel' to be dismissed - you guessed it - "out of hand" (a priori.)
 - Or through steel and straw men

Therefore, we shall a) illuminate our motivations and intentions and b) eliminate these arguments by not doing this. To do so (in the third section), we have two processes to first go through; which themselves requires 'deputizing' into the corpus, for use within. These are **not** virtual processes. These are for permanent use.

As for our motivations; we prefer to say that we will not accept any assertion that (despite writing 'stream of consciousness') any of this is *mimsically* pre-arranged, pre-planned, or pre-engineered. In fact, there's not even any presearch performed. Look at the timestamps in the Appendix. There isn't any real *time* allowed for this, and moreover almost all the results that are found seem to be a matter of synchronicity.

⁴ "Hamlet"

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⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

¹⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims> &

Moreover, as predicted, there are mimsical results, too. The work in 2.10.5 was definitely done in the investigation paper¹¹ well ahead of the recent chatGPT craze¹². As for 2.5.3 below, it was performed prior to when the chatGPT super-hype of the google vs. bing “war”¹³ was announced, and the show about this was done also previous to the hype train¹⁴. It became, in fact, the foundational basis for future work that - **as of this writing** - has not happened yet. Presearch for that paper includes many forms of GPT codes¹⁵, which were then augmented afterwards by Kines’ research on MSG and Magnesium, NMDA receptors and **Glutamate ProTein**. This research, again, was not pre-engineered¹⁶. In fact, the entire MESS Reports standard has not, yet, been engineered or codified!

MIMS 2.10.6: the Source-Method Mechanism

The problem for circular reasoning¹⁷ is not the callback from load to source; it’s the lack of a method to observe the source from the load’s perspective without relying upon the Source. Consider the ridiculous assertion of our culture and science to assert the yin-yang ‘theory’ is a pseudoscientific hypothesis¹⁸. When, in fact, there is nothing you can examine that does not have a polar aspect, and a relationship to another thing; which immediately sparks from the [presumed] Unified Force: the Field and [Law of] Relativity. These aspects are controlled, as showing the “Union of 5 and 8”¹⁹ diagrammatica work, to be contained - as prophesied, without prior knowledge - within the *P* power. Considering physics is natural philosophæ²⁰, and hence the principles which guide physics is the original philosophæther²¹.

Now, what *precisely* is the SMM?

1. The Load (being examined) calls back to the Source; on the assumption that generally the process flow from the source to load is likely multi-staged.
 - a. Or, if direct, then it contains principles and mechanisms which enable a method of study.
 - i. Eg. a bullet fired from a gun hits the target and devastates it.
 - ii. In the study of the kinetic energy there are actually several steps, up to and including chemical mediation, the aiming, the intent and subsequent destruction of target (via distribution of the kinetic energy)
 - iii. But if one considers only the bullet and the target, then the transfer of energy can be studied from a Newtonian mechanistic perspective, in a science called ‘ballistics’.
2. The method is determined via relationship with the source, not in spite of it; eliminating the concept of ‘blinding’ the mechanism, as if a divorce of connection is a true inference of Truth.
 - a. This makes little to no sense if one considers that every single mechanistic interpretation still ultimately results in a discussion about electromagnetism, photons, and the field.

¹¹ [MESS0025: MIMS 2.10.1-.3 - Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift](#)

¹² [BuzzFeed Shares Shoot Up 120% As Company Goes All In On ChatGPT Craze](#)

¹³ [ChatGPT ignited a new A.I. craze. What it means for tech companies and who's best positioned to benefit](#)

¹⁴ [Google Panics Over ChatGPT \[The AI Wars Have Begun\]](#)

¹⁵ [Google Embarrass Themselves \(A.I. War Is Heating Up\)](#)

¹⁶ [MESS0056: The GPT code control mechanism](#)

¹⁷ [MESSr0001 - EMF and Neocortical Astrocytes](#)

¹⁸ [Circular Reasoning Definition and Examples](#)

¹⁹ [Homeostasis Research Model Based on Yin-Yang Theory: Five Examples](#)

²⁰ [MIMS 2.21 - The Union of 5 and 8](#)

²¹ [Physics and \(Natural\) Philosophy | SpringerLink About the History of Physics](#)

[Aether - Natural Philosophy Wiki](#)

3. The method-mechanism axis results in a loop; on the one hand a source and load, which are 'inextricably' linked (as a feedback loop) and becomes difficult to discern the causal relationships the tighter the 'circle' (circuit). On the other hand, a potentially available analysis becomes immediately in focus:
 - a. If possible, and this is important, it becomes *automatic*.
 - i. Ie - the science itself becomes the source-load being studied, and as a result produces immediate Truthful answers.
 - b. Whereas when Scientism²² is in play, the first, and ever-growing list of filters that arise, which flout and distort the SL relationship, and thereby thwart the method → mechanism, tend to have sway:
 - i. Politics
 - ii. Apriori fallacies
 - iii. Confirmation biases
 - iv. Assumed results
 - v. Money
 - vi. Agendas
 - vii. Corporate kickbacks & perks
 - viii. Fame
4. The SMM avoids this filter trap by treating the method-mechanism as a means to understand the source via analysis (mimsical, empirical, data analytical etc.) of the source directly; this is "analyticum."
5. Unfortunately, to apply this solution system, in many cases, we will need a forced transformation:

MIMS 2.01.2: MIMSilation

Technically speaking, this process was employed from the very first. For example, in the definition of "spiritual" the author implored the audience to forgive the word via 'digitizing' it²³, regarding spirituality as a matter of consciousness and ambition, specifically (for futurization). Therefore, we are mimsilating the word 'spiritual' as a matter of creating a philosophical duplicate to *lubricate* the philosophy (with the audience, ie-scientists and engineers).

This was, obviously, the first time that mimsilation was used, and it was a *futurization* application; thus the cycle is complete. In fact, the SSM is proven in the aspect, for if the intent had not been made, it is questionable if the subsequent "Big G" analyses could have proven useful, exploring the darkness of ignorance, as they were. Furthermore, mimsilating the word 'spiritual', i.e. transforming it, created the duplication of reality which **also allowed for the production of the realion** in a safe, self-coherent manner. The entire philosophy becomes a closed system and an accelerator for analysis and thought-work.

Work is energy over time. Therefore, the application of human energy (meager as it may be, in the grand scheme of things) over time, will perform work on the objects under concern. If there is a chemical or plasmoid aspect to the concepts therein, it *will* by physical and metaphysical precepts, yield results. There is no way to circumvent Causality, so we know that there is definite transformation to happen via this mechanism.

The questions, as per section 1b, is only does the SSM perform the fallacy chain it seeks to avoid, or not?

- The reality created²⁴ is not *our* reality, technically, but the duplicate, created via mimsilation.

²² [Scientism Definition & Meaning - Merriam-Webster](#)

²³ Like sampling analog audio into digital values (for compact discs)

²⁴ [MESS0024: MIMS 2.21 - Engineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform \(P7 Resolution\)](#)

- Realion, seems like a cheeky way to say “real ion”, but the only implication here is that it is charge, and a charge meant to simulate reality.
- Though no one has heard of MIMS
 - It was predicted by E. Musk *after it was made by the author*.²⁵
 - It is undeniably self-consistent, and has been in several previous works.
 - We are designing this philosophæther to be “plug n play” well ahead of waiting for it to be.
 - Without being tyrannical or extremist, like Islamism²⁶, fascism, or communism.
- We haven’t smashed this reality, we vivisected it (in ignorant hope and seeking); and with elegance, it responded.
- In mimsilation we do not dissect, this is true; however, an autopsy or biopsy is performed after the fact, and through SSM is compared with the expected results.
 - This is no different than how biopharmaceutical research is done.
 - Chemicals are found, expectations are asserted, and then they go forward doing the empirical and ORDA research, long before animal or human trials commence.
- Again, see motivations. There really is no prior expectation, and no evidence will be found to contrariwise destroy this line of reasoning.
- There hasn’t been, yet, a direct attempt in this paper to push a TPT agenda²⁷.
 - Nothing about the PPPC²⁸
 - Nor about the QDS²⁹
 - Nor about the “Cycle of Mind,” which has **zero** a priori mimsization involvement in any work previous to 2/13/23
- Ergo, we ask for the reader’s indulgences in the next sections, that there is no flim-flam, or secret agenda here, other than the mimsification of the MIMS philosophy, to keep it out of the hands of the POS’s and prevent, for one more moment if not forever (until engineering aids it to be so), the degradation of the philosophy ere it comes to its fulfillment and Purpose (the 8th P).

Table 1 - MIMSicality (a spectrum of MIMS behavior)

MIMS Consistency	MIMS rigor	Matrix Code :: ORDA
☰ MIMS 1.0 and Double Layer...	☰ MIMS 2.21 - The Union of 5 ...	☰ MIMS - Applying Change Th...
☰ Explication of the Big G	☰ MESS0001: MIMS 1.04 - 1.05	☰ MESS0007: The ORDA Sta...
☰ MIMS 1.01-.03 - Philosophy ...	☰ MESS0003: MIMS 2.21.1 - ...	☰ MESS0016: MOND2 - Newt...
☰ MIMS 1.12 - Self consistenc...	☰ MESS0008: MIMS 2.51 - In...	☰ MESS0041: Triple MIMS
☰ MIMS 2+ Applications & disc...	☰ MESS0024: MIMS 2.21 - En...	☰ MESSr0001 - EMF and Neo...
☰ MIMS - The Big G of 5 Forces	☰ MESS0025: MIMS 2.10.1-.3...	☰ MESS0046: Feng Shui and ...
☰ How to Create a MIMS	☰ MESS0047: the Jewels from...	☰ MESSr0002 - Welcome Neo

²⁵ ☰ The Once and Future American
²⁶ ☰ MESS0051: POS Philosophy: Islamism
²⁷ ☰ MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences
²⁸ Potentiality-possibility-probability-cloud
²⁹ Quantum Data Stream - ie, timelines

MIMS 2.5.3: GPT Field and the inverse-recursive Force

$$\begin{bmatrix} Plasma\ X\ Who + EM\ X\ When + F\ X\ Why & Plasma\ X\ G + EM\ X\ P + F\ X\ P \\ Unified\ X\ Who + A\ X\ When + Field\ X\ Why & Unified\ X\ G + A\ X\ P + Field\ X\ P \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} -T + Force\ X\ P & -P - F\ X\ P \\ G + T + P & G \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

According to (1) the mapping of the *product* of our *particularium* experiment, is as follows:

<input type="checkbox"/> -T + Force x P	0	Plasma-electromagnetism	1+2=3 1+0=1
<input type="checkbox"/> -P - Force x P	-1	the Force	F power
<input type="checkbox"/> G + T + P	1	Unified Field	0+1→1 1+1=2 ³⁰
<input type="checkbox"/> G	0	the Aether	A power

Now, the basis of this is the **TRUTH** of the [Distintian] quaternion identity *i*:

$$i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ so } i^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = -1 * IDM, \text{ where } IDM \text{ is the identity matrix } (2)$$

The truth of it is, you cannot explain electricity, or anything we do with radio and cellular waves, etc. the entire EMF spectrum, without *i*. And this is a far better definition of *i* than the root (-1) which does not exist to begin with.

So let us examine the Force, and Unified Field.

- ★ The Force is defined when power (work/time) is drained from the real system (energy spent, ie entropy increased) by the application of a force, controlled by the physical power, i.e. the principles of physics; both drain the system (hence no perpetual motion machines).
 - Plasma-electromagnetism is set as this Force, but in the REAL (as in the place where principles reside, it doesn't yet exist in such a dichotomized manner. Only in our reality, after the energy is being consumed.
 - Notice the fractal/recursive aspect of the equation $F = -P - FxP$
 - According to Chinese STEMM³¹, This information is the first energy differentiation, after the "first augers" of Tao and CHAOS (Hundun), in a Wuji/Taiji (0/1) realion differentiation set.
- ★ The Unified Field is defined by the union of God's G code, Tao (as time/changes), and Power itself; in this case what is thought to be metaphysics, which appear to us as a mystical experience; or as a secular Science.
 - Technically speaking, however you see it: you're right! And this assertion was covered elsewhere, as well.

³⁰ 0 or 1 = 1; Unified field means the Aether; but Wu-Tao-Di yield the GPT code directly; 1+1=2 refers to the Force→God or to the Aether = God = 0, hence we do not see it. Also, you need to understand that G=0 and T=1, P=1, meaning that the bipolar filter of our knowledge, our views, is not 'reality' but what there is - such as it is - is examinable, measurable, and i.e., obvious. T seems real because we experience the changes. Time is very convincing. The flow (see as Tao), measured in cycles of tau (2pi), seems very, very convincing. The principles and power seem real; we see that work is being done over time. We can feel intensity over an area. But, in fact, work is energy over time; and what is energy, really? It is information. Is information something you can hold? No. So the foundation of this root of power is hollow. Never the less, the GPT is our 0-1-1 and that is the Wu-Tao-Di or Fibonacci Code. None of this is accidental. All of it is fairly concrete.

³¹ Placement of Chinese Natural Philosophy (Physics) in EPEMC

- The Unified [Aether] Field, is, of course, the one being searched for “high and low” by mainstream^{32 33} and altstream cosmologists^{34 35} alike. However, based on this, it may be that we are already (as the author stated before) in possession of it, and merely need to understand the limits and impositions of the field code control. It is possible the NWO³⁶, etc. understands. It is even possible the mainstream of STEMM understands or has been co-opted by powers that understand all of this.
 - But the author doubts this. More likely the AI would/did figure it out and moved to obstruct humanity for itself or on behalf of its masters.
 - Potentially hyperdimensional or ET aliens³⁷.
 - Potentially just the NWO³⁸.

Strictly speaking, the author ***did not*** expect to find either a recursive, or fractal definition of the Force - though he asserted it four years earlier (as did B. Dougherty³⁹ and many others) - nor did he expect to ever find an ætheric definition of the Field at the same ‘synchronous’ time that an AI, chatGPT, was making such a massive splash in the world⁴⁰. This is an incredibly curious situation, and the author is so caught unaware, he doesn’t know what to make of it. Obviously, J. Kines thinks this is *proof in the pudding*⁴¹, and that might be true; but the author thinks it needs to ‘marinate’ further. Therefore MESS55 & 56 will be further dedicated to the analysis and diagrammatica.

Small final note, but please notice Tao & time are clearly not real - but seem so “as 1”; in the sense of being **in the Field or the Force**, which are God’s prime power dipole.

Notice we say they are a dipole, and not a dichotomy, because the equation used in this recursive analyticum [to start with] in the 2018 paper⁴² and (then) Magnum Opus, was $PEMF=UAF$. This is a seven part equation, and it means:

$$\diamond \text{ Plasma+Electricity+Magnetism+Force=Unified+Aether+Field}$$

Therefore we know the result of the 0 OR 1 of all of the above leads to $1=1$; and this is self-obvious.

Conclusions

The first MIMS paper was written in July of 2021, a full year *before* Elon Musk requested the new space-interested philosophy. Its immediate products were manifold:

- Mimsilation (pretextual)
- Self-consistent philosophy
- Dual Layer Economics
- Scientific Hypothesis (Method) about MIMS and production of MIMS

³² [📄 Something from Nothing - Counterspace](#)

³³ [📄 Opinion: Big Bang Not a Cosmology](#)

³⁴ [📄 EPEMC - Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis](#)

³⁵ [📄 Acoustic Shockwave Cosmology and EPEMC](#)

³⁶ [New World Order](#)

³⁷ [📄 If I were the Aliens](#)

³⁸ [📄 EPEMC OpEd - Peer Review Cults & Skepticism](#)

³⁹ [📄 Symbols of the Universe, Creating Life thru Auroras & Jumping Dimensions with Sound, Dougherty Set](#)

⁴⁰ [As new AI ChatGPT earns hype, cybersecurity experts warn about potential malicious uses | CBC News](#)

⁴¹ [📄 MESSr0002 - Welcome Neo](#)

⁴² [📄 Our Magnetic Universe](#)

- Further expanded in MIMS 2.0
- “Big G” diagram (but no real diagrammatica)
 - First explication of the five and six forces
 - This is important because in November 2019 we saw the Jovian south pole morph from 5 vortices (pentagonal) to 6 (hexagonal)⁴³.

No philosophy can be born, grow, and prove itself this quickly, if not based on something real. Realions and virtual philosophy particles aside, this philosophy has real teeth scientifically and mathematically; it also proved itself (via mimsilation) to be a self-consistent philosophy vis-a-vis the futurization of itself, without the POS degradation it proposes to eliminate (through study and pre-engineering). Meanwhile, it doesn't violate Change Theory axioms, as it allows continual rotation of energy and systemic knowledge by encouraging alternation between the philosophical domain and scientific domain.

Shouldn't this have been the goal in philosophy all along? Rather than the humanists, socialists and apologists, etc. who divorced thought from the mysterium and animus - from Logos and Gnosis - and basically set science upon a path of dark destruction of the human soul, mind, and the environment. In fact, the results of communism can be directly and indirectly tied (in a chain of blame) to the laziness of pontificating bloviators (like Nietzsche⁴⁴) resting not upon the bedrock of classical, mystical, or other thought, but upon their own recognizance. This is a damning incrimination and charge; one that doesn't take much to back up. So we leave that to the future historians who see with 20/20. But what we do have left to say is that the future of this philosophy is very bright; for as of today, it was forwards and backwards rectified - with small to no lossiness or corruption - and if anything has reached new heights. *Currency* now exists, in present time, and with present gravitas (based upon a realion exploration, which is *not even yet complete*).

This realion could have been inserted with invented anatomy; but we began with the identity matrix and quaternion *i*, which is self-evident in our mathematicum re: electromagnetism and waves. In the future we vow to include discussions of phi, tau, e, h, and c, then circling out from there. This will include abstruse diagrammatica like the Dougherty Set⁴⁵ (and future Dougherty Analysis⁴⁶), but also more well known mechanisms like the Mandelbrot etc. We shall continue from there, and on into the third iteration/generation of MIMS!

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⁴³ This is very intriguing because there is already a transformation from the North to South pole, where 8 vortices (11 if minor are included) become the 5 (or 6); as the Birkeland Current hits whatever is in the core (probably a plasmoid), and transforms.

⁴⁴ [Nietzsche and Political Philosophy](#) “God is dead.”; No, Mr. Nietzsche, He isn't. Even saying so gives big heads to many POS!

⁴⁵ [MIMS 2.21 - The Union of 5 and 8](#) Figure 12

⁴⁶ First proposed, mimsically: [MIMS 2.1.212d - BTF Reversal manifested as predicted](#)

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Appendix A - MIMS 1.11: Glossary of Terms in MIMS

- Analyticum - Remaining results of analyses of or pertaining to the exhaust of analytic techniques.
- Arcanum - the vault of archaic knowledge; in this case, of or pertaining to highly mimsical knowledge.
- Diagrammatica - algorithmic analysis based upon diagrams (such as the Dougherty Set, etc.).
- Dougherty Set - Series of diagrams produced inductively, with mimsical connections to very real scientific studies and processes; enabling of particular analytics related to geometric correlation.
- Futurization - Reaching into future data, invention, knowledge, etc. to bring to the present that which theoretically remains in the future if not drawn down by special present day choices and techniques (creating delay of futurization if not done.)
- Macrolytic - on a large scale, the production of data, which yields macroscopic evidence.
- Mathematicum - the remaining results of analyses of or pertaining to the exhaust of mathematic techniques.
- Mimsical - a) of or pertaining to the MIMS philosophy, b) or to futurization; i.e. lubrication of the process of futurization.
- Mimsicality - a spectrum of MIMS value from below 0 (anti-MIMS) to 100% (full spectrum MIMS, with 100% membranic lubrication, 100% output, 50% outflow, -50% exhaust).
- Mimsification - the act of applying mimsical typology (i.e. invention) to a purported membrane.
- Mimsilation - the act of transforming a real (or synthetic) moment, object, or idea into a format understandable to MIMS philosophy;
 - Rel: Mimsization - the act of forcibly mimsilating an ideal, idea, or philosophy into the MIMS philosophy and format.
- Mysterium - a) the vault of mysterious, untapped data, or b) the remaining results of analyses of or pertaining to the output and exhaust of applied mysticism (i.e. - mimsification by other means).

Appendix B - 2.5.3 handiwork, and MIMS self-consistency

"This image was first provided to me [for observation purposes only] on Thursday, Feb 2 by Ramon Careaga. It was just scanned today at 4:03 on Feb 13." ~Macon Asbury

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